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VIU–CoARA Action Plan 2025–2028

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“Together, the members of CoARA are working to transform research assessment and create a more inclusive, impactful and sustainable research ecosystem for the global research community”

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1) National and International Context

There is broad consensus on the need to reform research assessment. The research community increasingly agrees that, in order to foster research quality and strengthen research environments, research assessment practices must be reviewed. This is due to several interconnected reasons:

- i) enabling assessment to support positive research cultures;
- ii) ensuring assessment practices remain relevant as research processes and expectations evolve; and
- iii) responding to growing societal, environmental, democratic and economic challenges.

Although the underlying motivations may differ, they all point in the same direction: reform is needed to continue supporting research quality.

In recent years, various initiatives have generated an international movement to reform research evaluation. The aim is to rethink how evaluation systems have traditionally addressed the inherent challenges of assessing scientific knowledge. Historically, these systems have relied heavily on bibliometric indicators of research output, based on the assumption that scientific knowledge is primarily expressed through publications. Quality has been inferred from peer review and from the influence reflected in citations.

Over time, the international scientific community has identified an excessive dependence on a small number of bibliometric indicators, resulting in significant limitations. Since the [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA, 2012\)](#) the international community has issued statements and manifestos, including the [Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics](#) (2015), o los [Hong Kong Principles](#) (2019), to open debate on how scientific output is evaluated and how assessment shapes researcher behaviour.

More recently, reforming research assessment has become a priority within the new [European Research Area \(ERA\)](#) driven by the European Commission since 2020. Among the 17 priority actions of the [European Research Area Policy Agenda: Overview of Actions for the Period 2022-2024](#), Action 3 focuses on reforming research assessment systems to ensure that research quality, performance and impact are assessed through fairer, more inclusive and diversified criteria. The action also emphasises recognising open science practices, including openness in collaboration and data sharing. These orientations align with the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) (2021). Furthermore, Action 13 highlights the necessary synergies between the ERA and the [European Higher Education Area \(EHEA\)](#). In they [Tirana Communiqué](#) (2024) of the Bologna Process, Ministers of Higher Education reaffirm the importance of reviewing criteria and indicators for academic career assessment.

In line with this political commitment, at the end of 2021, the European Commission published the report [Towards a reform of the research assessment system: scoping report](#), which explores the needs and recommendations for reforming research assessment in Europe. In this same vein and in line with the priorities established in the ERA, this document sets out the principles on which evaluation criteria and processes should be based, promoting a fairer, more inclusive and representative approach to the technological, economic, cultural, environmental and social quality and impact of scientific work, beyond the academic sphere.

In 2022, following an extensive participatory process, the European Commission published the text of the Institutional Agreement for all organisations wishing to actively join the Reform of Research Assessment: [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment \(ARRA\)](#). The drafting and writing of the Agreement were coordinated by the [European University Association \(EUA\)](#) and

[Science Europe](#), which led the drafting work, together with a group of representatives from the research community across Europe. The publication of the agreement in July 2022 was the result of collaborative work and a consultation process involving more than 350 organisations from over 40 countries. This document sets out the direction for change in the evaluation practices of research, research staff and research organisations with the aim of improving the quality and impact of scientific output, as well as creating a more equitable and effective research environment that fosters innovation and scientific progress.

On 1 December 2022, the International [Coalition for the Advancement of Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) was formally established through the accession of the international institutions that signed the ARRA. Based on the debate and consensus of the international community, CoARA seeks systemic reform of research assessment and improvement of assessment practices, with the application of shared principles and clear commitments that should bear fruit in the coming years. As of 2 December 2025, a total of 794 organisations from around the world have joined CoARA, including universities, research centres and associations, research funding bodies, national and regional research evaluation agencies, as well as scientific and academic staff associations.

Currently, the coalition's work is organised around 13 [Working Groups](#), which address specific issues (e.g. academic careers, infrastructure, multilingualism, responsible metrics, etc.), and 18 [National Chapters](#). In the case of Spain, the Spanish Chapter has been created, led by the [National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation \(ANECA\)](#), the [Conference of Rectors of Spanish Universities \(CRUE\)](#) and the [Higher Council for Scientific Research \(CSIC\)](#), with the support of the Ministry of Universities (initially) and the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities (later), and with the participation of more than seventy organisations, including VIU (<https://www.universidadviu.com/es/actualidad/noticias/viu-se-adhiere-coara-y-su-national-chapter-spain-para-impulsar-el-avance-de-la-evaluacion-de-la-investigacion>).

This **Spanish Chapter** includes the [Testimony of the National Forum](#) for Research Assessment Reform, which met for the first and only time in January 2023 at the University of Barcelona (UB). Currently, the Spanish Chapter brings together more than **60 institutions, 35 of which are universities**. Its work is organised into **four Working Groups**, dedicated respectively to evaluation methodologies and criteria, multidisciplinary and interdisciplinarity, and awareness-raising and training. These groups operate in line with **Commitments 6, 7 and 8** of the Agreement, aimed at reviewing evaluation tools and processes, strengthening collaboration between actors in the scientific system, and promoting mutual learning both within the Chapter itself and with the CoARA Working Groups. The **VIU joined the Spanish Chapter in April 2024** and actively participates in **Working Group 4**, which focuses on awareness-raising and training actions. In addition, the Spanish Chapter published its [latest report](#) in September 2025, consolidating the progress made and defining the priorities for the next implementation period.

At the national level, notable contributions and regulatory changes regarding academic evaluation are expected in 2023. On the one hand, the new [Organic Law on the University System \(LOSU\)](#) incorporates modifications to the faculty accreditation system (which are then articulated through [Royal Decree 678/2023](#)) and specific criteria regarding the promotion of open science, which must be incorporated into the evaluation systems by quality agencies. On the other hand, one of the strategic objectives of the first [National Open Science Strategy \(ENCA\)](#) 2023-2027 is to establish new research evaluation mechanisms and a system of incentives and recognition to promote open science practices. In order to incorporate these regulatory changes, ANECA set up the [Commission for the Evaluation and Monitoring of the State Accreditation Procedure](#) to enable the adaptation of the current evaluation system and fulfil the commitments made to DORA and CoARA. In July 2024, in compliance with the commitments

made upon joining CoARA, ANECA's management presented the [2024-2027 Action Plan](#) to its Governing Council, which includes details of the actions and activities that the Agency is committed to implementing during this period in order to move towards a new culture of evaluation of research activity in all its diversity.

2) Strategies for the Promotion and Development of Research at the International University of Valencia

Research, together with teaching and knowledge transfer, is an essential function of the International University of Valencia (VIU). This triple mission is legally recognised in [Law 3/2022](#), of 22 July, which amends [Law 7/2008](#), of 13 June, on the **Recognition of the International University of Valencia**. Article 2.2 establishes that *“the VIU shall have an appropriate teaching, research and management structure for the development of distance learning, in accordance with its internal rules of organisation and operation”*.

In line with this institutional vision, [Decree 73/2015](#), of 15 May, of the Consell, approves the **Rules of Organisation and Functioning of the VIU**. Article 3.6 of this decree recognises *“the University's aspiration to position itself as an institution within the information and knowledge society, promoting the creation, dissemination and transfer of knowledge through research, development and innovatio”*. Furthermore, Article 6 establishes that *“the university may create different organisational structures (such as departments, institutes, chairs or centres) with the aim of effectively carrying out its teaching and research activities”*.

With the institutional growth and consolidation of VIU, [Decree 190/2019](#), of 13 September, allowed for the formal creation of new faculties and the Higher School of Engineering, Science and Technology. Thus, [Decree 166/2020](#), of 30 October, introduced an update to the **Rules of Organisation and Functioning**, incorporating new academic structures and governing bodies that strengthen the university's research and management capacity.

This regulatory and organisational evolution has been accompanied by the implementation of various strategies aimed at promoting and consolidating research activity at VIU. These initiatives include the **Internal Research Project Funding Plan**, the **Scientific Production Incentive Plan** and the **Research Excellence Plan**. In addition, mechanisms have been established for the recognition and evaluation of the different [Research Groups](#), which ensures their quality and guides their efforts towards strategic objectives.

Since 2023, the university has expanded its academic offering in the field of research by implementing various [Doctoral Programmes](#) across all Faculties and Schools. It has also promoted the creation of [Research Chairs](#) and the operation of specialised bodies such as the **Research Committee**, the [Research and Teaching Ethics Committee \(CEID\)](#) and the **Research Activity Evaluation Committee (CEAI)**. These bodies guarantee scientific integrity, academic quality and the proper evaluation of research performance.

The institutional commitment to research and knowledge transfer is also reflected in the **Faculty Teaching Career Plan**, where research activity is integrated as an essential component of professional development. This reinforces VIU's social responsibility to its academic and professional communities of reference and aligns its mission with national and international standards of excellence.

Within this framework, the evaluation activities carried out at VIU serve six fundamental purposes, each supported by specific processes and tools:

1. **Monitoring and financing of research structures**, including the evaluation of groups, chairs, institutes and centres, as well as the allocation of merits and budget distribution.

2. **Promotion of research** through communication and visualisation of results.
3. **Selection and recruitment of research figures** within the framework of the Research Excellence Plan.
4. **Reductions in teaching load** for faculty in order to facilitate the development of research activities.
5. **Individual recognition** through **Research Awards** and the **Scientific Production Incentive Plan**.
6. **Evaluation of research projects and plans**, including the **Supervision of Doctoral Theses** and the management of associated mentions and recognition.

Taken together, these strategies demonstrate a strong and well-structured institutional policy for the promotion of research, in line with the principles promoted by CoARA.

2.1. Research Groups

Research Groups are the primary driving force behind the various research activities carried out at VIU. These groups underpin scientific output (including articles in academic journals, book chapters, conference papers and similar contributions) and are responsible for participation in both internal and external research projects, as well as research contracts and any other research activity with academic and/or social impact.

VIU maintains a permanent call for the recognition of **Research Groups**, thereby facilitating synergies and collaborations among Academic and Research Staff (*Personal Docente e Investigador*, PDI). These Research Groups may also incorporate members from other external institutions, organisations and companies, with the aim of fostering fruitful collaborations with the various actors within the research ecosystem. All of this is framed within the strategic objective of strengthening research, development and innovation (R&D&I) activities and the associated organisational structures.

At present, VIU has **88 Research Groups** across all areas of knowledge in which teaching is delivered: health sciences, business, law, education sciences, arts and humanities, science and technology, and communication.

Three types of Research Groups are recognised, based on the experience and joint track record of their members:

- ✓ **Emerging Research Groups:** These are newly established groups with no prior experience of joint collaboration among their members, or with only limited collaborative experience, but with shared future-oriented research interests that enable them to define research lines and develop research activity.
- ✓ **Consolidated Research Groups:** These are groups with an established joint research track record and experience in the implementation of research, development and innovation (R&D&I) projects, as well as in the scientific dissemination of their research results.
- ✓ **Excellence Research Groups:** These are groups with a strong joint research trajectory in one or more research lines, demonstrating extensive experience in participation in competitive projects at both national and international level, as well as in R&D&I contracts with companies. In addition, the group's research activity leads to research outputs with high academic and/or social impact.

The International University of Valencia conducts an annual monitoring of the activity of its **Research Groups**, based on a set of specific criteria that allow for a comprehensive assessment of their scientific performance. **This evaluation process is aligned with the principles of CoARA**, promoting a qualitative, transparent and inclusive assessment focused on the real impact of research, beyond purely quantitative metrics.

2.2. Internal Research Project Funding Programme

En In 2019, VIU established a **Research Funding Scheme**, which included the **Internal Research Project Funding Programme**. This programme is designed to promote research, development and innovation (R+D+I) activities through an annual call, providing funding of up to **€5,000 per awarded research project**.

Since its inception, internal research projects have been funded across a wide range of **thematic areas**, including: the prevention and psychosocial and neuropsychological intervention of substance and non-substance addictions; studies in education and health addressing socio-emotional aspects and their relationship with behaviours in childhood, adolescence and adulthood that lead to the onset of disease; research on non-communicable diseases related to nutritional imbalances; metagenomic studies on the impact of the microbiota and its alterations on human health; musicology; educational innovation; cyberbullying; and linguistics, among others.

All information on funded internal research projects is available through the [VIU Research Portal](#).

2.3. Scientific Output Incentives Plan

One of VIU's objectives in the field of research is to support, promote and strengthen high-quality research activity and scientific output among its **Academic and Research Staff (Personal Docente e Investigador, PDI)**, recognising the importance of such activity as a driver of personal, institutional and social development through its academic and/or social impact.

To this end, the **Scientific Output Incentive Plan** was established. This is an annual call that recognises and financially rewards high-impact scientific output produced by VIU academic staff, through a system of economic incentives. The assessment of contributions is based on the evaluation criteria published annually in the *Boletín Oficial del Estado* (BOE) for the recognition of research performance periods (*sexenios*) by the **National Commission for the Evaluation of Research Activity (CNEAI)** of the **National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation (ANECA)**, which serve as benchmarks and quality indicators for the assessed outputs.

The programme is open to VIU academic staff who meet the eligibility requirements established in the regulations governing the call.

2.4. Research Excellence Award

VIU implements a range of actions aimed at incentivising and recognising the research activity of its **Academic and Research Staff (Personal Docente e Investigador, PDI)**.

In this context of support and incentive for research activity, an **annual call for Research Excellence Awards** was approved by Rectoral Resolution dated **13 January 2021**. This initiative constitutes an additional form of recognition for the merits and research work carried out by the university's academic staff.

Aligned with recent changes in research assessment introduced by ANECA in accordance with the CoARA and DORA initiatives, the evaluation focuses on the **five most significant scientific**

contributions achieved during the year of the call. Applicants are required to demonstrate the relevance and impact of these contributions through a **narrative description of merits**, accompanied by the corresponding indicators associated with each merit.

The programme is open to VIU academic staff who meet the eligibility requirements established in the relevant regulations. The same evaluation criteria as those applied in the Scientific Output Incentive Plan are used for assessment purposes.

2.5. Research Chairs

[VIU Research Chairs](#) play an important role not only in the field of research, but also in training and in the dissemination of knowledge.

Research Chairs also serve as a forum for interaction and collaboration with companies, research groups and other stakeholders seeking to advance a specific field of knowledge addressed by each Chair.

On this basis, VIU is developing a Network of Research Chairs aimed at serving audiences committed to social development through research, including the following:

- ✓ [Chair in the Humanisation of Healthcare](#), whose main objective is to promote teaching, research and knowledge dissemination in the field of healthcare humanisation. In addition, the Chair seeks to establish the necessary links between academic, social and business institutions in order to achieve a positive impact on the humanisation of healthcare across all its dimensions.
- ✓ [VIU–NED Chair in Global Neuroscience and Social Change](#), whose primary objective is to promote teaching, research and dissemination in the field of neuroscience and social change. Among its objectives, the Chair prioritises the “**Global Surgery 2030**” programme, with the aim of promoting neurosurgery as an enabling specialty for the other disciplines included within the advancement of Global Surgery. The activities of the Chair contribute not only to improving medical and surgical care in general, but also place a particular focus on low-income countries, where surgery is essential for achieving the **Sustainable Development Goals**.
- ✓ [Planeta Chair in Literature and Society](#), which constitutes a space for the dissemination and transfer of knowledge on literature at VIU and serves as a catalyst for social debate on creative literacy. Its objectives include promoting research and reaffirming literature as a humanistic advancement and a form of social commitment, in collaboration with VIU’s HUMA Centre. It also seeks to reflect on the impact of technologies within the literary context, contribute to improving the use of the Spanish language, and foster broad-based reading practices.
- ✓ [Chair in Audiovisual Culture](#), which constitutes an inter-university academic platform and a research space focused on audiovisual culture in its social, economic and ideological context, in connection with other forms of cultural expression. It was established by the **Consell de l’Audiovisual de la Comunitat Valenciana, CEU Cardenal Herrera University (CEU-UCH)** and VIU, with the aim of supporting decision-making by the **Consell de l’Audiovisual de la Comunitat Valenciana (CACV)** in the field of audiovisual media.

2.6. Doctoral Programmes

The [VIU Doctoral School](#) was established on 2 December 2022, in accordance with the provisions set out in Article 9 of [Royal Decree 99/2011](#) of 28 January, which regulates Official

Doctoral Studies in Spain. Its establishment was notified to the Ministry of Education through the Directorate-General for University Policy, for the purposes of its registration in the [Register of Universities, Centres and Degrees \(RUCT\)](#), governed by [Royal Decree 1509/2008](#) of 12 September.

The primary objective of the VIU Doctoral School is to deliver high-quality programmes that train researchers committed to excellence and capable of responding to current needs and future scientific challenges. The Doctoral School is an active member of the [European University Association \(EUA\)](#) and forms part of the [PRIDE Network – Association for Professionals in Doctoral Education](#), an organisation representing the community of doctoral education professionals in Europe.

VIU currently offers three doctoral programmes:

- ✓ [Doctoral Programme in Immunonutrition, Nutritional Genomics and Food Science](#): This programme integrates nutrition within a holistic vision of health, addressing the therapeutic potential of food. It trains researchers who study diet and the interactions between the immune and genetic systems in order to improve societal quality of life.
- ✓ [Doctoral Programme in Public, Community and Addictions Health](#): This programme focuses on training researchers to address emerging challenges in public, community and addictions health, with a strong emphasis on the transfer and translation of research outcomes to individuals, families and communities as a whole. It adopts a **One Health approach** to improve health–disease outcomes and overall wellbeing, among other priorities.
- ✓ [Doctoral Programme in Data Science and Big Data](#): The primary objective of this doctoral programme is to train researchers whose specialisation focuses on one or more stages of the data life cycle. This includes research into data collection and structuring techniques, data processing, data analysis using machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques, the development of data visualisation methods, and the optimisation of these processes for large-scale data volumes.

VIU's doctoral programmes adopt an approach aligned with the principles of CoARA, promoting a broad and responsible vision of research activity. This approach is reflected both in the typological diversity of doctoral theses—including interdisciplinary, collaborative and innovative studies—and in the strengthening of the international dimension, by encouraging joint supervision arrangements (*cotutelle*), co-supervision with international institutions, and publication in globally oriented research contexts.

In addition, VIU actively supports advanced research training through specific grants for research stays at centres of excellence, as well as through its own [Scholarships and Grants Programme](#) and through participation in the **Santander Scholarships** scheme. Likewise, the university promotes the effective integration of doctoral candidates into its consolidated Research Groups, as well as into ongoing competitively funded projects, facilitating their participation in high-impact collaborative research dynamics and fostering their professional development within demanding scientific environments committed to excellence and research integrity.

2.7. Research Committee

The VIU Research Committee is a non-binding advisory body whose purpose is to advise the Vice-Rectorate for Research, Transfer and Internationalisation (VRITI) on matters relating to the university's scientific policy, general research plans, strategic priorities, and the allocation of

the research budget, as well as on the launching and awarding of research grants and funding schemes by the University.

The Research Committee is composed of the members of the VRITI and one representative from each Faculty/School (Research Coordinators). The composition of the Research Committee was approved by the Rector and the Director General of the University through a [Rectoral Resolution](#) dated 4 March 2022, in accordance with [Decree 166/2020](#) of 30 October of the *Consell*, concerning the New Organisation and Operating Regulations of the International University of Valencia, which, in **Article 12.3**, establishes that the *Governing Board* may delegate such powers as it deems appropriate for the proper internal functioning of the University.

2.8. Research and Teaching Ethics Committee (CEID)

[The VIU Research and Teaching Ethics Committee \(CEID\)](#) has the mission of ensuring that research projects and teaching activities carried out at the University comply with the methodological, ethical and legal requirements established for research involving human participants and the use of personal data.

Furthermore, the Committee formally certifies such compliance before the relevant authorities through an opinion issued by an impartial and independent evaluation committee. This **Committee for the Evaluation and Monitoring of Research Involving Human Participants (CEISH)** is the collegiate body responsible for assessing the ethical, methodological and legal aspects of research and teaching activities conducted at the International University of Valencia.

2.9. Committee for the Evaluation of Research Activity (CEAI)

In April 2024, the International University of Valencia, actively engaged in the European and global debates on the need to reform research assessment models, formally joined the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#). As part of this accession, the University committed to developing a **four-year institutional action plan**, aligned with the principles of the **Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA)**, which was signed on the same date.

Within this reform process, **transparency and objectivity in evaluation procedures are actively promoted**, including the implementation of clear procedures and well-defined standards for assessing research quality, as well as the involvement of independent and specialised evaluation committees. Furthermore, the diversity of merits and career paths is recognised, valuing both basic and applied research and promoting a balanced approach between the two.

With the aim of aligning evaluation processes with the principles of transparency, collaboration and accessibility inherent to open science, and thereby promoting more robust, relevant and socially engaged research, VIU has established the **Committee for the Evaluation of Research Activity (CEAI)** as a collegiate body that safeguards these principles and is responsible for the evaluation of the research activity of the University's Academic and Research Staff.

This Committee is entrusted with the task of evaluating and issuing a prior, mandatory and binding report on the quality of the research activity carried out at the University. It is a collegiate body that stands out not only for the technical capacity and professional expertise of its members, but also for their impartiality and independence.

3) VIU CoARA Action Plan

3.1. Principles Guiding the Plan

The 2025–2028 Action Plan constitutes the first institutional proposal of the International University of Valencia (VIU) aimed at improving the evaluation of research activity. Its objective is to promote an evaluation model that recognises and fosters research quality, performance and impact at both academic and societal levels, thereby strengthening public trust in the research and innovation system and in its outcomes.

This strategy is aligned with the commitments undertaken by VIU following its accession to CoARA, and is grounded in the conviction that an appropriate evaluation system should not only incentivise research excellence, but also contribute to its recognition and long-term sustainability. For this reason, all actions envisaged in the Plan (see Table 1) **mainstream the Four Core Commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA)**, which the University has endorsed:

- ❶ **Recognise the diversity of contributions and research career paths**, taking into account their context and nature.
- ❷ **Prioritise qualitative evaluation**, primarily based on peer review, complemented by the responsible use of quantitative indicators.
- ❸ **Abandon the inappropriate use of metrics based on journal and publication impact**, in particular the misuse of the **Journal Impact Factor (JIF)** and the **h-index**.
- ❹ **Exclude institutional rankings as a tool for research assessment**.

The implementation of these principles is structured around three operational approaches:

- **Principle of prudence.** The regulatory changes introduced by the [Organic Law of the University System \(LOSU\)](#) and [Royal Decree 678/2023](#) are beginning to modify the evaluation criteria for Academic and Research Staff (*Personal Docente e Investigador*, PDI), with a foreseeable evolution over the coming years; these changes should therefore be progressively integrated into VIU's evaluation system. However, the **2025–2028 Action Plan does not initially incorporate measures relating to the individual assessment of research performance of VIU academic staff**. This approach may nevertheless be reviewed and adjusted in future annual updates of the Plan.
- **Principle of realism.** At this initial stage, the Plan focuses on areas over which VIU has direct competence, such as the improvement of its own competitive research calls (including calls for research projects and for the recruitment of predoctoral and postdoctoral research staff), as well as the evaluation of research groups and research units.
- **Continuous evaluation and improvement.** The Plan incorporates mechanisms for ongoing review and updating, allowing actions to be adjusted in light of achieved results and emerging needs. Annual reviews will enable the assessment of the implementation of changes, the improvement of evaluation procedures and criteria, and the provision of constructive feedback to both evaluators and those being evaluated. Annual monitoring reports will make it possible to adapt work plans and strengthen the transformative impact of the reform process.

3.2. Proposal for the VIU CoARA Action Plan

The VIU CoARA Action Plan proposed for the 2025–2028 period aims to underpin the University’s commitment to open and responsible research, aligning its institutional mission and vision with the principles of transparency, rigour and ethics promoted by CoARA.

This Plan sets out a range of strategies and actions aimed at strengthening a culture of high-quality, accessible and responsible research within the VIU academic community.

The priority actions of VIU’s 2025–2028 Action Plan are summarised in Table 1, which brings together the CoARA commitments, lines of action, specific actions, timelines, responsible bodies and the methodology for evaluating the actions.

Table 1: VIU–CoARA Action Plan. Commitments 1–4 are described in Section 3.1

CoARA Commitments	Lines of Action	Actions	Timeframe	Responsible Unit	How will it be evaluated?
5 Commit to reforming research assessment at the institutional level to achieve the organisational changes undertaken	Development, implementation and monitoring of the VIU–CoARA Action Plan	Creation of the VIU–CoARA Commission for the implementation and execution of the Action Plan	2025 - 2028	VIU–CoARA Commission	Biannual meetings and validation of the semi-annual and annual reports
		Monitoring of the execution of the Action Plan by the Academic Governing Council and the VRITI	2025 - 2028	VIU–CoARA Commission	Submission of the annual monitoring report
		Allocation and monitoring of the execution of budgeted actions included in the VIU–CoARA Action Plan 2024–2027	2025 - 2028	Vice-Rectorate for Research, Transfer and Internationalisation (VRITI)	
6 Review and develop criteria, tools and processes for the evaluation of research	Review and updating of internal calls (evaluation criteria, use of indicators, evaluation guidelines, etc.), in accordance with CoARA principles	Internal calls for research projects	2025 - 2028	Research Results Transfer Office (OTRI)	Annual review conducted by the VIU–CoARA Commission of the published call, including its criteria and required documentation, together with an overall analysis of its outcomes from a CoARA perspective.
		Internal calls for teaching and educational innovation projects	2025 - 2028	Vice-Rectorate for Teaching and Educational Innovation	
		Internal calls for the selection of predoctoral and postdoctoral staff	2025 - 2028	Vice-Rectorate for Research, Transfer and Internationalisation (VRITI)	
		Scientific Output Incentive Plan	2025 - 2028	Research Results Transfer Office (OTRI)	
		Research Excellence Award	2025 - 2028	Research Directorate	
		Evaluation of VIU Research Groups	2025 - 2028	Research Directorate	
		Doctoral programmes	2025 - 2028	Doctoral School Directorate	
		Evaluation of the research activity merits of Academic and Research Staff (PDI)	2025 - 2028	Committee for the Evaluation of Research Activity (CEAI)	
7 Raise awareness of research assessment reform and ensure transparent communication, together with guidance and training on evaluation criteria, evaluation processes and their application.	Development of internal support materials to ensure alignment with CoARA principles	Preparation of guidelines for the submission of internal calls, revised and adapted to the CoARA perspective	2025 - 2028	VIU–CoARA Commission	Guidelines for each of the revised internal calls
	Communication strategy of the Action Plan	Drafting of a specific communication plan for the Action Plan	2025	Vice-Rectorate for Research, Transfer and Internationalisation (VRITI)	Communication plan
		Implementation of internal communication actions envisaged in the specific communication plan	2025 - 2028	Vice-Rectorate for Research, Transfer and Internationalisation (VRITI)	Internal communication actions
		Implementation of external communication actions envisaged in the specific communication plan	2025 - 2028	Vice-Rectorate for Research, Transfer and Internationalisation (VRITI)	External communication actions
	Training related to CoARA principles	Training actions linked to the different research activity evaluation processes, such as research performance periods (sexenios), research excellence awards, accreditation processes, projects, among others	2025 - 2028	Research Directorate	Annual training activities (at least one per year)
8 Exchange practices and experiences that enable mutual learning, within and beyond CoARA	Communication and feedback mechanisms with CoARA	Participation in the CoARA General Assembly	2025 - 2028	VIU–CoARA Commission	Annual summary of participation in CoARA
9 Communicate progress and adherence to the principles and the implementation of the commitments		Participation in the Spanish CoARA Chapter	2025 - 2028	VIU–CoARA Commission	Annual summary of participation in the Spanish Chapter
Participation in other CoARA working groups and committees, or in other national or international research assessment groups		2025 - 2028	VIU–CoARA Commission	Annual summary of participation in CoARA working groups and other CoARA-related forums	
10 Evaluate practices, criteria and tools on the basis of robust evidence and the most up-to-date research on research assessment, using open data to gather evidence and generate new research.	Evaluation and continuous improvement of the reform process	Analysis of the results of successful initiatives or evaluation proposals applied to VIU's internal calls	2025 - 2028	VIU–CoARA Commission	Annual review conducted by the VIU–CoARA Commission and publication of the results
		Monitoring of successful initiatives or innovative research assessment proposals at national and European level	2025 - 2028	VIU–CoARA Commission	
		Analysis of the results of the experience and final evaluation of the changes implemented during the initial years of the reform	2025 - 2028	VIU–CoARA Commission	

3.3. Governance and Monitoring

The actions aimed at reforming research assessment will be supervised and implemented within the budgetary framework and strategic objectives of the Vice-Rectorate for Research, Transfer and Internationalisation (VRITI).

The proposed Plan will be:

- ✓ **Shared and discussed with the members of the VIU–CoARA Commission**
- ✓ **Reviewed and endorsed by the Research Committee**
- ✓ **Submitted to the Academic Governing Council (CGA) for approval**

Between July and September 2025, the VIU–CoARA Commission will be established (see Annex I). It will be composed of a wide range of profiles, including representatives from the various Vice-Rectorates of VIU; representatives from the Department of Communication and Content; researchers; technical staff; and a broad spectrum of specialists in open science, ethics, scientific and technical fields, scientometrics, research assessment and related areas. The Commission will be responsible for the implementation, monitoring and annual updating of the Plan. It will meet on a regular basis and will be structured around three Working Groups (WGs):

WG1: Analysis of criteria and methodologies for the evaluation of research activity at VIU.

WG2: Awareness-raising and communication of CoARA commitments.

WG3: VIU strategy in relation to CoARA.

On a semi-annual basis, the Technical Secretariat of the Commission will present to the Commission a detailed report on the actions implemented, in collaboration with the different Vice-Rectorates of VIU, research centres and the Doctoral School, as well as with the relevant areas and operational groups. Over the following six months, the implemented actions and the planned actions will be reviewed.

On an annual basis, the actions set out in this Plan will be reviewed by the Commission, which may amend, remove or introduce actions in response to VIU's needs. The annual activity report and any proposed modifications to the Plan will be submitted to the VRITI and the CGA before being forwarded to CoARA.

ANNEX I. VIU–CoARA Commission

Misión: The mission of the **VIU–CoARA Commission** is to adapt the commitments on research assessment to the VIU context through an in-depth institutional analysis that enables the design of a **flexible and multidimensional evaluation framework**, and its progressive integration into VIU’s research assessment practices.

Objectives: The VIU–CoARA Commission will be established between July and September 2025 with the following objectives:

1. **To review and align the current system for evaluating research activity with the open science paradigm**, taking into account the diversity of activities and outputs of scientific activity, such as: open access to research results; transfer to the business sector, public administrations and society; science communication and scientific culture; among others. These aspects are currently considered integral to research activity, and the aim is to define objective and weighted indicators of relevance for their assessment.
2. **To consider research processes and contexts**, taking into account interdisciplinarity and multidisciplinary, the gender dimension, social impact, training, mentoring, and related aspects.
3. **To act in a coordinated manner with other international actors** (international CoARA, DORA, etc.) and **national stakeholders** (ANECA and CRUE) involved in the implementation of the new parameters defined for the evaluation of research activity.
4. **To equip VIU with the methodologies, culture and tools necessary** to achieve these objectives.

Composition: The VIU–CoARA Commission will be composed of a range of profiles with diverse areas of expertise, organised into three Working Groups:

- 1) **Working Group on the analysis of VIU research assessment practices:** criteria and methodologies
- 2) **Working Group on awareness-raising and communication of CoARA commitments**
- 3) **Working Group on the VIU strategy for adopting CoARA commitments**

Through these actions, it is expected that during 2025 the Commission will develop a proposal for evaluation practices and implementation methodologies, an agenda of actions and the resources required to carry out this proposal, as well as a training and communication plan.